

**A new species of *Condica* Walker, 1865 from the Arabian Peninsula
(Lepidoptera: Noctuidae)**

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Abstract – *Condica ilniczkyi* sp. nov. (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae: Condicinae) is described from the Sultanate of Oman.

Key words – owlet moths, Condicinae, taxonomy, species description, Oman

INTRODUCTION

Two Hungarian expeditions led to the Sultanate of Oman in 2009 and 2018 resulted materials included three specimens of an unknown species of the genus *Condica* Walker, 1856 (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae: Condicinae). The dissection of the genitalia proved that these specimens represent a species distinct from the externally similar *Condica autophiloides* Hacker, 2011. The description of the new species is given below.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Adults were captured at 125W HgLI mercury vapour lamp light. The set specimens were photographed with Nikon 2–50 camera with AF–5 Micro, Nikkor 60 mm objective. Genitalia were dissected following the technique of ROBINSON (1976) modified by FIBIGER (1997). Abdomens were macerated in 12% solution of potassium hydroxide (KOH) for one night before dissection. The cleaned genital capsule, the everted vesica and the female copulatory organs were dehydrated in 96% ethanol; weakly sclerotised structures were stained with eosine. The dehydrated organs were mounted in Euparal on slides. Slides were photographed using an Olympus SZX12 photographic microscope; digital images were adjusted using Adobe Photoshop.

Abbreviations: HNHM = Hungarian Natural History Museum, Budapest; SJS = private collection of Sándor Jenő Simonyi, Budapest.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Condica ilniczkyi sp. nov.

(Figs 1–5)

Type material – Holotype: male (Fig. 1), “Oman, Dhofar, about 20 km W of Al Mughsayl, above the Highway No. 47, N16°51’11.52”; E53°43’04.45”, h: 496 m, 29.X.2018, leg. Levente Ábrahám, Sándor Ilniczky and Sándor Jenő Simonyi”; Slide No. 616m S. J. Simonyi (Fig. 4). Paratypes: two females (Figs 2–3), same locality, 13.X.2009, leg. Sándor Ilniczky and Sándor Jenő Simonyi; Slide No. 612f S. J. Simonyi (Fig. 5). The holotype and the dissected paratype are deposited in the HNHM as well as their genitalia slides, the other paratype is in SJS.

Diagnosis – The new species resembles *Condica autophiloides*; but the colouration and pattern of the wings as well as the structure of the male genitalia are significantly different. The forewing ground colour is darker greyish yellow, the antemedial and postmedial crosslines are strongly marked, and the basal and medial areas are rather dark in *Condica ilniczkyi* sp. nov. (Figs 1–3), while the forewing ground colour is significantly lighter, rather pale straw-yellow, and the crosslines are poorly visible in *Condica autophiloides* (HACKER *et al.* 2011: pl. 31, fig. 4). The male genitalia are similar in the two species (Fig. 4, HACKER *et al.* 2011: 268, fig. 6) in having similarly built uncus and tegumen, a medially positioned harpe, and similar structure of juxta; the latter structure is missing from other related *Condica* species (cf. HACKER *et al.* 2016: pl. 137, fig. c). The valva of the new species, however, is distally broader and pointed apically (it is distally tapering in *Condica autophiloides*, terminating in a blunt and rounded end); the narrow, tapering membranous section of valva being parallel with the ventral margin is longer, almost reaching apical margin of valva (it is terminated at 70 % of the distance between the harpe and the apical margin in *Condica autophiloides*); the aedeagus is curved (it is almost straight in *Condica autophiloides*); and the strong cornutus of the vesica is only slightly arched while it is hook-like in *Condica autophiloides*. (The female of *Condica autophiloides* is unknown.)

Description – External morphology (Figs 1–3): Wingspan 20 mm (male), 25–27 mm (females). Ground colour of head, body and forewings greyish yellow, forewings with variably intense dark gray irroration. Costal and subapical spots dark brown, continuing in diffuse stripes in and below cell; basal and median areas with darker grey suffusion. Crosslines dark greyish, antemedial and postmedial lines double, wavy; subterminal line obsolescent; fringes chequered with grey. Underside of forewings pale greyish yellow, middle of costal area, apical streak and lateral margin darkened. Upperside of hindwing of male yellowish with fine grey irroration and rather narrow darker greyish marginal area; that of female with stronger grey suffusion. Fringes of hindwing chequered (white with light grey spots).

Figs 1–5. *Condica ilniczkyi* sp. nov., morphology, 1 = habitus of holotype male, deposited in the HNHM, 2 = habitus of paratype female, deposited in the HNHM, 3 = habitus of paratype female, deposited in SJS, 4 = male genitalia of holotype, slide No. 616m S. J. Simonyi, 5 = female genitalia of paratype, slide No. 612f S. J. Simonyi (photos by Gábor Ronkay (Figs 1–3), and Balázs Tóth (Figs 4–5))

Male genitalia (Fig. 4): Valva scarcely hairy, distally broader, cucullus broadly triangular, finely curved dorsad, its apex asymmetrically, slightly pointed; harpe positioned medially on valva, long and slender, apically slightly dilated and flattened; juxta rather quadrangular with fine dorso-lateral extensions and bifurcate ventro-lateral appendages, tip of its dorso-medial thorn-like extension projecting towards vinculum. Aedeagus more or less cylindrical, wide and slightly curved; caecum very small; strong cornutus of vesica only slightly arched.

Female genitalia (Fig. 5): Ovipositor short and rather narrow; papillae anales comparatively big, pear-shaped, somewhat swollen, gently hairy; apophyses posteriores slightly bent, stick-like with narrow, wedge-shaped basal plates and blunt ends; apophyses anteriores a little longer. Penultimate segment very short (ca. 15% of entire length of ovipositor); its two dorsal plates continued in a narrow and strongly sclerotised, U-shaped ribbon extending ventrally towards antrum, forming a sclerotised rim of ostial ring. Antrum narrow, slightly conical, sclerotised; ductus bursae thin, membranous, joining to tubular distal section of corpus bursae aside appendix bursae. Appendix bursae membranous, saccate, more or less oval, its length ca. 3/4 diameter of fundus bursae and ca. 2 times broader than distal tubular section of corpus bursae. Corpus bursae entirely membranous, its distal section long, tubular, proximal section (fundus bursae) more or less globular, with long, narrow signum antero-laterally.

Fig. 6. Type locality of *Condica ilniczkyi* sp. nov. (photo by Sándor Jenő Simonyi)

Bionomics and distribution – The type material of *Condica ilniczkyi* sp. nov. was collected in a steep, rocky, grassy and sparsely bushy hillside above Fazaya beach. The mount is flanked by a very deep, turning gorge. The type locality is found about 20 km W of Al Mughsayl, above the Highway No. 47, at 496 m altitude. The climate of this area is under the influence of monsoon during July, August and September. Adults are on the wing during October (Fig. 6). Preadult stages and foodplants are unknown.

Etymology – The new species is dedicated to Dr. Sándor Ilniczky who organised and led numerous joint expeditions to Oman.

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